

A Simple Method of Isolation of Bacteria—Free Cellulolytic Soil Fungi

D. N. DAS and* MANJULIKA CHANDRA

Department of Applied Chemistry, University Colleges of Science and Technology, Calcutta University, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 5 August 1980, accepted 15 July 1981

Pure cellulolytic soil-fungi free from bacterial contaminants have been isolated (streaking-method) on selective enriched agar media with powdered cellulose as carbon source and containing a mixture of four antibiotics, penicillin G, streptomycin, oxytetracycline and chloramphenicol each at a concentration (γ /ml) 20, 50, 200 and 200 respectively. The method is simple and needs minimum time, labour and material.

DEEP interests have been noticed recently in researches on microbial saccharification of celluloses to glucose for possible production of energy-chemicals, pharmaceuticals and other chemicals. Many laboratories are engaged in isolating potent cellulolytic strains from soil or otherwise and treatment of celluloses to increase the degree of saccharification. Pure cellulolytic culture free from contaminants inclusive of bacteria is an essential requirement for studies on isolation and production of cellulolytic enzymes. Hungate¹ questioned the purity of cellulolytic cultures isolated so far. He laid down the standards for obtaining pure cellulolytic cultures on selective enriched medium with cellulose as the carbon source.

Methods^{2,3,4} so far used for isolation of cellulolytic cultures were all based on the use of selective enriched media containing cellulose as the carbon source. We found these methods to be labourious as they needed many serial dilutions, streakings on a large number of plates and sometimes even then the isolates were not totally free from bacterial contaminations. Moreover, it is to be admitted that occurrence of contaminants inclusive of bacteria in cellulolytic fungi isolated by selective enriched media, is not completely ruled out too.

In this paper we report on the use of a selective enriched medium with combiotics for quick isolation of some cellulolytic soil fungi completely free from bacteria.

Experimental

Soil (collected from a local garden) suspension (0.1%) was made in sterile distilled water. A loopful of this suspension was aseptically streaked consecutively on six plates containing selective enriched agar media⁵ with 0.3% powdered cellulose (Carl Schleicher and Schuele, W. Germany). The plating media also contained four antibiotics, namely, penicillin G, streptomycin, oxytetracycline and chloramphenicol. Growth appeared after 48 hrs of incubation in dark at 28-35° under humid conditions.

Fungal colonies on every plate were examined microscopically with crystal violet for detecting the presence of any bacterial contaminant. Further checks for the presence of bacteria were made by streaking the isolates on nutrient agar. Pure isolates free from any bacterial contaminant were routinely obtained on the 1st plate of streaking. Cellulose digestion zones were produced by these isolates when they were cultivated on a thinner selective medium¹ for a longer period of incubation.

TABLE 1—OBSERVATIONS ON THE ISOLATION (BY STREAK PLATE METHOD) OF SOME SOIL FUNGI ON SELECTIVE ENRICHED AGAR MEDIUM

Order of plates streaked**	Observations*	
	With antibiotics***	Without antibiotics
1st	Isolated fungal**** colonies free from bacterial contamination	Innumerable spreading as well as non-spreading discrete bacterial colonies mixed up with fungal colonies
2nd	Same as above	Fungal colonies contaminated with bacterial colonies
3rd	Same as above	Same as above but with lesser bacterial contamination
4th	Same as above	Fungal colonies associated with bacterial colonies
5th	Same as above	Fungal colonies isolated showed bacterial contaminations
6th	Same as above	Most fungal colonies still showed bacterial contamination though to a lesser extent. Very rarely, however, some fungal colonies were found free of bacterial contaminations

* Based on visual and microscopic observations from 12-18 plates.

** With single charging of inoculating loop (without recharging it). Eight back and forth streakings, 2 cm apart, were made on the surface of each plate.

*** Mixture of antibiotics as stated in the experimental section: various combinations consisting of 2 or 3 antibiotics at the respective concentrations were tried but none was found capable of complete prevention of bacterial contamination as the combination of all the four antibiotics together.

**** Cellulolytic yeasts were found in a very few instances with the cellulolytic moulds and were removed by further streaking. Most of the cellulolytic fungi detected were true moulds and some actinomycetes.

By trial and error it was found that most satisfactory isolation needed a mixture of the four antibiotics and the minimum concentrations (γ /ml) needed were as follows : penicillin G, streptomycin, oxytetracycline and chloramphenicol at 20, 50, 200 and 200 respectively. All antibiotic solutions were freshly prepared before use.

A summary of our observations on the isolation of some cellulolytic soil fungi using combiotic enriched selective media is recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the observations recorded in Table 1 that inclusion of a antibiotic mixture containing penicillin, streptomycin, oxytetracycline and chloramphenicol at the concentrations used in the selective enriched agar medium helps in isolating cellulolytic fungi completely free from bacterial contaminant. The fact that none of the combinations consisting of 2 or 3 antibiotics only could completely prevent bacterial occurrence in the selective medium like the combination of the four antibiotics is clearly indicative of the presence of multiple antibiotic resistant bacteria in the soil. In spite of these types of antibiotic resistant bacteria in soil, bacteria resistant to all the four antibiotics simultaneously would be rare if not mathematically impossible at all. This fact seems to form the basis of our present success with the combiotic medium

in completely eliminating the bacterial contaminants in the isolates of cellulolytic fungi. Separate experiments on comparative enzymatic (cellulolytic) studies of all the isolates obtained following the present method showed⁵ that the use of the antibiotic mixture did not affect enzyme productions in shake-flask cultures. The present method appears to be a simple, inexpensive and faster way of isolation of cellulolytic fungi free from bacterial contaminants. It further seems that a similar approach of selective enriched medium with combiotics could be used for pure isolation of different physiological types of soil fungi free from bacteria.

Acknowledgement

One of us (M. C.) is thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, India for financial help.

References

1. R. E. HUNGATE, *Bact. Rev.*, 1950, 14, 1.
2. J. PELCZAR (Jr) and R. D. REID, in "Microbiology", 3rd ed, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1972, p. 143.
3. H. O. W. EGGINS and G. J. F. PUGH, *Nature*, 1962, 193, 94.
4. A. K. HAZRA, S. K. BOSE and B. C. GUHA, *Sci. and Cult.*, 1958, 24, 37.
5. M. CHANDRA and D. N. DAS, *Soc. Biol. Chem. Abst.*, 48th Annual General Meeting held at Lucknow, 1979, p. 137.